
Defamation on Whatsapp Story Text: A Forensic Linguistics View

Titissugiyantiningtyas¹, I Wayan Pastika², I Wayan Simpen³, I Nengah Sudipa⁴

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Abstract

Social media especially whatsapp has become a new dynamic in communicating. Besides being able to be used to send messages, WhatsApp can also play a role in facilitating the spread of wrong content. This study aims to examine lingual data related to defamation obtained from texts that can be categorized as having defamatory content on whatsapp social media . Data were analyzed based on forensic linguistic studies, namely semantics, both lexical and grammatical semantics, and pragmatics. The findings of this study are based on semantics and pragmatics which are part of forensic linguistics including: (1) based on lexical semantics found the meaning of lexical denotations; (2) based on grammatical semantics found the meaning of phrases, sentences, which refer to defamation ; (3) there are speech act components in whatsapp story text. Based on the results of the study it was concluded that the form of language crime speech in whatsapp social media often occurs.

1. Introduction

Language is a major element in conveying information to others. The function of language is not only as a means of communication, but also as a tool for self-expression, a tool for integration, social adaptation, and a tool for social control. Language essentially has values and norms in its delivery both in official and non-official forums in everyday life both in spoken and written forms. In communicating using language, speakers not only sort the language according to their conditions, but also must consider social norms and moral values in every utterance. The statement emphasizes

¹ Universitas 17 Agustus 1945 Banyuwangi, Indonesia. E-mail: titissningtyas@gmail.com

² Linguistics Professor, Universitas Udayana, Denpasar, Indonesia.

³ Linguistics Professor, Universitas Udayana, Denpasar, Indonesia.

⁴ Linguistics Professor, Universitas Udayana, Denpasar, Indonesia.

that, as a human being who has reason, thoughts, and feelings, he should be careful when it comes to language.

At present, people are given the convenience of communicating by using social media. Social media is a medium for socializing with each other and is done online which allows every human being to interact with each other without being limited by space and time. However, the fact is that there are irregularities in the use of social media. Social media is a means to attack the honor or good name of other parties.

One of the social media that is often used by the public is whatsapp. WhatsApp users can carry out communication practices such as sending messages, creating stories, commenting, and even creating group chats. Along with the development of information and communication technology, cases of language crime, one of which is defamation, are often found on WhatsApp social media networks. Niknik M. Kuntarto (2020) states that the criteria for pragmatic defamation in society are containing insults, containing insults with diction that can affect reputation, insults that are known to others, insults related to many people, and associating with someone's disgrace or the badness of someone who is suspected.

Fundamentally, forensic linguistics can be defined as the scientific study of language phenomenon data applied to forensic contexts. Forensic linguistics attempts to analyze language data to determine the meaning of a written or utterance, the intent contained therein, and the owner of the written or utterance. To analyze WhatsApp story text, two branches of linguistics are used, namely semantics and pragmatics. Semantics examines the meaning of language contained in diction, phrases and sentences. In forensic linguistics, semantic analysis is used more to uncover the meaning of words or expressions that may be difficult to understand. These difficulties occur usually because of ambiguity in the diction, phrases, or sentences used. Chaer (2009) explains that lexical semantics is a branch of semantics that examines the meaning of words independently, without linking the position of the word in the sentence. While grammatical semantics, namely semantics that studies the meaning of phrases, clauses, and sentences.

Apart from semantics, the linguistic theory used to study WhatsApp story text is pragmatics. In pragmatic studies, speech act is a central unit. Searle (1969) describes five categories of illocutionary speech acts, namely:

1. Assertive, namely the form of speech that binds the speaker to the truth of the proposition for what is expressed.
2. Directive, the form of speech intended by the speaker to influence the speech partner to take action.
3. Commissive, a form of speech that functions to express promises.
4. Expressive, a form of speech that functions to express or show the speaker's psychological attitude towards a situation.
5. Declarative, form of speech that connects the contents of speech with reality.

With a focus on forensic linguistic studies, this paper will present 1) based on lexical semantics the meaning of lexical denotation is found; (2) based on grammatical semantics found the meaning of phrases, sentences, which refer to defamation; (3) there are illocutionary speech acts in whatsapp story text.

2. Materials and Methods

The source of this research data comes from whatsapp stories in December 2022. The subject of this research data is WhatsApp story text taken via screenshots. Data collection methods are divided into two, namely the method of documentation and observation methods. This study uses a

descriptive qualitative methodological approach and a theoretical approach from semantics and pragmatics, specifically illocutionary speech acts.

3. Results and Discussions

The results of the analysis carried out on whatsapp story text based on two branches of linguistics, namely semantics and illocutionary speech acts Searle (1969) are as follows:

(1) *Gawe koen Maulida*

Mbok pikir aku meneng seperti sing mbok bayangkan. Lek aku bener gak wedi setan aku

For you Maulida

You think I'm just as quiet as you imagine. If I really do not fear the devil I am.

Context: Pipink defamed Maulida through whatsapp stories because she felt cheated or lied to.

Based on linguistics, first from lexical semantics, diction in data (1) is interpreted according to KBBI V online as follows:

For	:	is a preposition to express for
You	:	being spoken to; who is greeted (in a familiar or rude variety)
Maulida	:	is a person's name
think	:	said to himself; opinion (consideration); think
I	:	pronoun who speaks or writes (in familiar variety); self; I.
shut up	:	silent (speaking), motionless (staying in place)
just	:	always; continuously
like	:	as well as; not change
Which	:	a word that states that the next part of the sentence explains the word in front
imagine	:	describe in fantasy
If	:	conjunctions to mark gestures
Correct	:	as it is (should be)
No	:	particle to express denial, rejection, denial, and so on
Afraid	:	dare not (do, take, suffer, and so on)
demon	:	evil spirit (which always tempts people to do evil)

Second, grammatical semantics, that is, grammatical words cannot stand alone. Even a grammatical word can only find its meaning when it is side by side with other words. 'for you Maulida' includes a coordinating phrase. A coordinating phrase is an endocentric phrase with many main components, which potentially can be connected with the conjunction 'for'. 'You think I'm as quiet as you imagine' is a subordinating clause. The conjunction 'like' used in this clause causes one clause to become part of another clause. 'if I really am not afraid of demons I' is a conditional subordinate clause. The conjunction 'if' used is a conjunction to connect language elements which are used to connect language elements that have a conditional meaning.

Third, pragmatically. Data (1), the speech acts contained in the speech spoken by Pipink to her speech partner, Maulida. Through this speech, it can be determined that the speech leads to Maulida with the aim of being known by whatsapp users. In this utterance, there is assertive illocutionary. Assertive speech acts are speech acts that function to express something. Based on the assertive identification used by the speaker, the action of "declaring" is found. The action states that the speaker will not remain silent, he will take an action to his speech partner, besides that the speaker also states

that if he is true he is not afraid of anyone including Satan. In data (1) the form of a grammatical unit which shows a defamation associated with someone's disgrace (Maulida).

- (2) This is the dajjal,
how to deal with this person can not use the heart, he's half demon

Context: Pipink defamed Maulida through whatsapp stories because she felt cheated or lied to.

Based on linguistics, first, from a lexical semantic point of view, the diction in data (2) is interpreted according to the online oxford dictionary, as follows:

This	:	a pointer to something that is not far from the speaker
Person	:	human (in a special sense)
Dajjal	:	'dajjal' is a non-standard form of 'dajal' bad manners; fraudster; liar
No	:	'no' is a non-standard form of 'no' particle to express denial, rejection, denial, and so on; gone
Can	:	able (power to do something); can
Use	:	wearing
Heart	:	what you feel inside
method	:	a way (rule, system) of doing (doing and so on) something
face it	:	fight, compete with
half	:	half
devil	:	spirits who always try to lead people astray from God's guidance; demons; demon
the question	:	make a question

Second, grammatical semantics, that is, grammatical words cannot stand alone. Even a grammatical word can only find its meaning when it is side by side with other words. 'These are the Dajjal' grammatically 'these are the people' is the subject and 'the Dajjal' is the predicate. This sentence refers to the problem being discussed by the uploader of the whatsapp story, namely about a lie, fraud, and people who have bad behavior. 'You can't use your heart to deal with it, it's half a demon', is a non-restrictive attributive relationship clause. Where this clause only provides information on the noun it describes. So, sentences with relative clauses that serve as additional information are enclosed in commas.

Third, pragmatically. Data (2), the speech acts contained in the speech spoken by Pipink to her speech partner, namely Maulida, are related to data (1). Through this speech, it can be determined that the speech leads to Maulida with the aim of being known by whatsapp users. In this speech, there is expressive illocutionary. Expressive speech acts are speech acts that function to state or show the speaker's psychological attitude towards a situation. Based on the expressive identification used by the speaker, it is found that the act of "reproaching/insulting" is found. The speaker uses expressive speech acts to criticize/insult the speech partner (Maulida).

4. Conclusion

The results of the whatsapp story text analysis show that lexical and grammatical semantic analysis contains dictions that have negative and insulting meanings. Likewise, analysis using the illocutionary speech act approach shows that the data contains assertive and expressive illocutionary speech acts. Thus it can be explained that the statement uploaded by the speaker is an insult that is

seen or read by other whatsapp users so that it can be categorized as defamation. Defamation is a process, method, act of defaming or defaming; dirt.

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